

UDC 658.2

JEL classification: B41; M21; H51

THEORETICAL REVIEW OF DEVELOPING INNOVATIVE MARKETING STRATEGIES

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ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ ОБЗОР ПО ВЫРАБОТКЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ МАРКЕТИНГОВЫХ СТРАТЕГИЙ

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Abstract. The article discusses the theoretical issues of developing an innovative strategy. The author has reviewed the scientific literature on this topic. Also, the statistics of the number of technological, marketing and organizational innovations introduced in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2008-2016 has been given. At the end of the article, the author outlined legal acts for the development of innovative marketing in the country, and also suggested a number of measures for the further development of the development of an innovative marketing strategy.

Аннотация. В статье приведены теоретические вопросы выработки инновационной стратегии. Автором проведен обзор научных литератур по данной тематике. Также, проведен приведена статистика числа технологических, маркетинговых и организационных инноваций, внедренных в Республике Узбекистан за 2008-2016 гг. В конце статьи автором изложены правовые акты по развитию инновационного маркетинга в стране, а также предложены ряд мероприятий по дальнейшему развитию выработки стратегии инновационного маркетинга.

Keywords: innovative marketing, efficiency, innovation, entrepreneurship development.

Ключевые слова: инновационный маркетинг, эффективность, инновация, развитие предпринимательства.

Introduction

The fastest introduction of modern innovative marketing technologies in the branches of economy, social and other spheres, using effective marketing methods, is an important prerequisite for the accelerated development of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The rapid development of the market for goods and services necessitates marketing based on modern innovative approaches and technologies that will ensure the competitiveness of the country in the world market.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from September 9, 2018 "On Approval of the Strategy for Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019 - 2021", PF-5544, "Towards achieving the entry of Uzbekistan into the top 50 most developed countries in the world by rating of Global Innovation Index" a number of other tasks have been identified. Effective performance of these tasks implies the elimination of scientific, methodological and practical problems in our enterprises aimed at the development and implementation of innovative marketing strategies.

Material and research methods

In scientific literature, there are widespread methods of the marketing strategy of enterprises in terms of their product, type of activity, the efficiency of their economic activity, or the extent to which their marketing activities are undertaken. The universally accepted methods of assessing competitiveness «Improving product quality» are seen as a major factor [5]. The Japanese model uses the same methods as "marketing activity", while American methods use more "market leadership" or "market share assessment" methods, although the main focus of the Japanese model is the "refinement of the quality system" [6].

The main features of the Japanese model are based on the study of the suitability of the product to the consumer demand, the French model "marketing competition" the extent to which the organization's marketing activities are checked for compliance with the production. The main feature of the American model of competitive evaluation is the market position of the enterprise and its market opportunities. In the European Union, one of the most reliable indicators of competitiveness is the assessment of the long-term productivity and productivity of enterprises [7].

Results and discussion

A series of research studies on the development and implementation of marketing innovations in the world practice has been conducted and the study of their methodological basics will increase the ability of local enterprises to develop appropriate approaches to the development of innovative marketing strategies.

The first scientific innovation innovation innovation was introduced by Theodore Levitt in 1960 and argued that it would have an impact on the efficiency of its operation.

In the world of large companies and their laboratories, many innovative products are created, but they are very few in marketing innovations. Innovations in marketing are often unknown, unplanned, and random, out of the central nucleus due to coincidences.

Innovations are the main means of ensuring the competitiveness of the enterprise and increasing its economic efficiency. Innovations, in turn, are characterized by product, process, organizational and marketing innovation.

Most research focuses on product, process and organizational innovation. The growing competition in the global market has led to the study of marketing innovations, demonstrating the process of enterprise growth, competitiveness and strategies. However, this does not mean that marketing innovations are no longer the case, but in the general sense of the notion of such concepts, and in other normative documents, that is, in the manual of the OSLO (OBJECTIVES AND SCOPE OF MANUAL) guidelines. Accordingly, in 2005 the OSLO manual was introduced as a separate section of marketing innovations and was reflected in the statistics of the countries of the world in statistical reporting.

In marketing strategies, however, less attention is paid to marketing innovations. The marketing capacity of the company is determined by the increase in sales of goods and services. The focus is on collecting, distributing, analyzing and protecting the environment. Innovative marketing and marketing competitiveness are interconnected concepts. Marketing plays a key role in ensuring competitiveness, and marketing is also a usual role within a competitive strategy.

Marketing opportunities not only provide innovative development but also help them to succeed in the innovation market. As marketing innovations were incorporated into the OSLO Guidelines, the collection of marketing innovation enabled researchers to conduct research in various fields. Therefore, it is important to note that research in this area is not sufficiently effective in the countries of the world. Particular attention should be paid to the fact that research on marketing innovations is conducted mainly in Europe and Asia. Scientists in our country, especially

in the USA, have not done enough research on this issue, and research on methodological bases for the development and implementation of innovative marketing strategies is not enough.

It is a great effort to keep in mind the differentiation and efficiency of the efficiency of enterprise management, through the introduction of innovation in the production process, and the awareness of new and new products, with the introduction of innovative technologies in marketing. "[3] According to Live with, marketing innovations are viewed as a process that is neglected by businesses and comes about by itself or by some coincidence.

Many studies have pointed out that it is unlikely that economic productivity will be achieved by going beyond the product innovation, that is, by simply linking it to it.

In general, it is important to develop a systematic approach to marketing innovations that need to be widely studied. These conceptual approaches can be seen in a comprehensive analysis of innovative marketing and its importance as a marketing branch.

When looking at the methodological guidelines for marketing innovation, the following questions need to be grasped:

- What marketing innovations are and how they are transformed during the lifetime of the industry;
- How influencing marketing innovations to increase competitiveness and market leadership in the enterprise.

What synergistic effect is the result of the introduction of marketing innovations?

These issues require the understanding of marketing innovations, the dynamics of their development, the frequency of industry growth, the comparison of product or process innovation with marketing innovations, and the identification and development of interconnected development and change.

In the following, the impact of marketing innovations on enterprise development will be studied and the effectiveness of product innovation and innovation on marketing innovations will be assessed. Continuous introduction of marketing innovations with innovation in productivity is a topical issue because the old ways to market new products do not sufficiently yield. The use of old marketing methods in the market with new products does not allow for a sufficient level of sales of new goods.

The use of marketing innovations creates opportunities for added value, reduction of costs, and increasing the cost of new products and services [5].

In general, marketing innovations should be considered as business processes in the organization of marketing activities, communication, value creation, and customer relationship management.

As mentioned above, the law of dynamics in marketing innovations applies. This dynamics can be changed in three-step (bottom, growth, and specific), at which innovations can be changed relative to the production process (Figure).

According to Figure, the innovation activity of enterprises is primarily dominated by brand innovation. But at the next stages of innovation development, there is a rapid growth in marketing innovation, either of economic development or marketing innovation. In most cases, businesses are focused primarily on product innovation, with less emphasis on marketing innovation. However, the results of the growing competition in the market make it increasingly possible to increase the level of marketing innovation and make the companies more productive.

Figure. The dynamics of marketing innovation

In the industrial sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 4762 innovations have been implemented in 2008-2016, of which 4620 are 97% technological innovations, 1.7% — marketing innovations and 1.3% — innovation innovations (Table).

Table

THE NUMBER OF TECHNOLOGICAL, MARKETING AND ORGANIZATIONAL INNOVATIONS INTRODUCED IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN FOR 2008-2016

Years	Total innovations	Including		
		A total of technological innovations	Marketing	Total innovation innovation
2016	981	976	0	5
2015	889	866	16	7
2014	882	837	35	10
2013	693	665	19	9
2012	288	264	10	14
2011	307	300	1	6
2010	248	243	0	5
2009	231	226	0	5
2008	243	243	0	0
Total	4762	4620	81	61

Source: Data of the State committee of State Statistical Committee of Uzbekistan. (25.09.2018). <http://stat.uz>.

The country's industrial enterprises have implemented 81 marketing innovations in 2008-2016, mainly covering the period 2012-2015. In recent years, there has been an increase in organizational innovation. In the country, in 2016, 1816 innovations have been implemented in all sectors, including 51 marketing innovations and 39 organizational innovations. The most prominent marketing innovation industry is the communication and information network, with its share of total marketing innovation reaching 45%, ie 23.

Conclusions

The results of the analysis show that the introduction of effective marketing innovations in the economy of Uzbekistan, in particular, the industrial sector, is a key issue on the agenda, and it is desirable to pay particular attention to:

- Increasing the number of marketing and consulting firms serving the B2B market, and promoting the integration of industrial enterprises with them;
- Establishing "Innovative Centers", "Innovative incubators" in industrial enterprises, with the development of educational institutions, and the creation of separate departments dealing with marketing innovations in their activities;
- Use and effective use of benchmarking in this area developed and developed by foreign companies in accordance with national characteristics and effectively applying innovative marketing technologies;
- Development of innovative marketing strategies aimed at promoting product innovation in the market;
- Establishment of the special units of the Ministry of Innovative Development aimed at the development of marketing innovations, established by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 29, 2017 "On Establishment of the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. UP-5264;
- By implementing these tasks effectively, our country will be able to further develop its economy, increase the production of competitive products, and increase the reputation of local brands in the global markets.

Acknowledgments:

I am grateful to my colleague Ph.D. Hakimov Ziyodulla for his innumerable contribution to the preparation of this article. Also, I express my gratitude to the colleagues of the "Marketing" department in the moral support of my research.

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*Работа поступила
в редакцию 11.10.2018 г.*

*Принята к публикации
16.10.2018 г.*

Ссылка для цитирования:

Sharipov I. Theoretical review of developing innovative marketing strategies // Бюллетень науки и практики. 2018. Т. 4. №11. С. 269-274. Режим доступа: <http://www.bulletennauki.com/sharipov-1> (дата обращения 15.11.2018).

Cite as (APA):

Sharipov, I. (2018). Theoretical review of developing innovative marketing strategies *Bulletin of Science and Practice*, 4(11), 269-274.